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**Capital Structure Determinants of the Food and Allied Industry -
An Empirical Study in Bangladesh**

CAPITAL STRUCTURE DETERMINANTS OF THE FOOD AND ALLIED INDUSTRY - AN EMPIRICAL STUDY IN BANGLADESH

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Abstract

The purpose of this paper is to identify the determinants of capital structure in the food and allied industry of Bangladesh. Eight independent variables - Firm Size, Profitability, Liquidity, Tangibility, Operational Ability, Sales Growth, Tax Shield, and Earnings Volatility were identified through literature review and their significance as determinants of Firm Leverage was tested using Regression Analysis. 14 companies listed in the Dhaka Stock Exchange under the Food and Allied sector were analyzed using data from a 5 year period. Liquidity, Tangibility, and Tax Shield were found to be significant variables and all three had negative relationship with leverage. Using Pearson's Correlation analysis, only Liquidity and Profitability were found to be significantly correlated to Leverage. The findings of the study were also compared with the predictions of the Pecking Order Hypothesis and the Trade-off Theory. Some of these findings were consistent with the Trade-off Theory, while others supported the Pecking Order theory. The causes of these inconsistencies were beyond the scope of this study and further research is recommended on this topic. This study should serve as a starting point for future researchers and as a reference point for policymakers, financial managers, and investors involved in the food and allied industry of Bangladesh.

Key Words: *Capital Structure, Dhaka Stock Exchange, Food and Allied Industry of Bangladesh, Pecking Order Theory, Trade Off Theory.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Capital structure refers to how a business firm finances its business operations, whether through internal financing or external financing. Long-term debt, short-term debt, common stock, preferred stock, and retained earnings are all sources of funds that can be used by a firm to define its capital structure. There have been a number of researches over the past decades to determine which factors have significant impact on the capital structure of a company. Numerous researchers from different countries have identified a number of factors to be significant determinants of the capital

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structures of firms operating in different industries. This research is a similar attempt to find out which factors play significant role in determining the capital structures of the firms operating in the food and allied industry of Bangladesh.

Bangladesh is a market-based economy and is considered to be one of the Next Eleven emerging market economies (O'Neill, Wilson, Purushothaman, & Stupnytska, 2005). With an annual growth rate of 7.1%, Bangladesh was the second fastest growing major economy of 2016 according to the International Monetary Fund (IMF). The food and allied sector of the country, though still underdeveloped, is growing rapidly on par with the overall economy of the country. According to the Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics (BBS), the food industry employs 19 percent of the industrial manufacturing workforce in Bangladesh and contributes approximately 2.01 percent to the overall GDP of the country. Yet there appears to be a lack of research on the capital structure determinants of this industry.

This research tries to answer the question of which factors are most significant in the capital structure decisions of the companies listed in the food and allied sector of Bangladesh. The literature review section discusses some popular capital structure theories and empirical research findings from other countries. The methodology section describes the regression model and independent variables used to explain the capital structure decisions in the food and allied sector of Bangladesh. The results and discussion section compares the actual findings of the research with the theoretical expectations. The conclusion section summarizes the key findings of the research and recommends future actions.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Modigliani and Miller (1958) argues in their pioneering research that capital structure is irrelevant in determining the value of a firm in an efficient market with no taxes, agency costs, bankruptcy cost, transaction costs, or asymmetric information. According to their research, the value of a firm remains unaffected whether the firm uses debt financing or equity financing. However, subsequent research has found this theorem to be inconsistent with real world observations. In the real world, factors such as the tax shield of debt can greatly affect the overall value of a firm.

Right now, the two prevailing theories in regards to capital structure are the Trade-off Theory and the Pecking Order Theory. The Trade-off Theory of capital structure states that companies must find a balance between the tax saving benefits of debt and financial distress to arrive at an optimal capital structure that maximizes firm value. Whenever a firm uses debt financing, its value increases as a result of tax benefits. However, it also raises its bankruptcy costs. The classical Trade-off Theory can be traced to Kraus and Litzenberger (1973), who were among the first

researchers to consider the balance between the tax saving benefits of debt and the dead-weight costs of bankruptcy.

The Pecking Order Theory was popularized by Myers and Majluf (1984) as an alternative to the static Trade-off Theory. According to this theory, cost of financing increases with asymmetric information. Thus, firms prefer internal financing (i.e. retained earnings) over external financing. This goes against the general assumption of the Trade-off Theory that a firm will prefer debt financing over retained earnings because of the increased tax benefits. The Pecking Order Theory also proposes that firms will prefer debt financing over equity financing if external financing is required.

While both the Trade-off Theory and the Pecking Order Theory remain quite popular, real world tests of these theories regarding capital structure decisions have shown mixed results (Shyam-Sundera & Myers, 1999; Chirinko & Singha, 2000; Frank & Goyal, 2003). Baskin (1989) observed empirical evidence supporting the Pecking Order Theory that established firms prefer debt financing over new equity issuance. However, Helwege and Liang (1996) asserts that firms with access to capital market do not follow the pecking order hypothesis when choosing what type of securities to offer to the public.

Sogorb-Mira and López-Gracia (2003) argues that the Trade-off Theory offers better insight than the Pecking Order Theory when analyzing the capital structure decisions of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Spain. Conversely, Tong and Green (2007) found that the Pecking Order Theory performs better than the Trade-off Theory in identifying the determinants of leverage for Chinese companies. This implies that capital structure determinants can differ from country to country and industry to industry.

According to Chen (2004), neither the Trade-off Theory nor the Pecking Order Theory holds true in determining the capital structure decisions of Chinese-listed companies. Unlike the Western firms, the capital choice decision of Chinese firms seems to follow a new pecking order of retained earnings, equity financing, and long-term debt.

According to Bauer (2004), the significant determinants of capital structure decisions in the Czech Republic are Size, Profitability, Tangibility, and Growth Opportunities. Among these four variables, Size was found to be positively correlated with Leverage, while the other three were found to be negatively correlated. Tax Rate and Non-debt Tax Shield were not found to be significant determinants of the capital structure decisions in the Czech Republic.

Bevan and Danbolt (2007) found that larger companies are more likely to use debt financing than smaller companies. They also found that more profitable firms are less likely to take long-term debt, while tangibility positively influences both long-term

and short term borrowing. However, growth opportunities were not found to be significant determinants of long-term borrowing decisions in the United Kingdom.

Akbar and Bhutto (2012) found both Growth and Size to be significant determinants in the capital structure decisions of Pakistani non-financial firms and both factors were positively correlated to Leverage. Profitability, Tangibility, Tax Shield, and Earnings Volatility were not found to be significant according to their research.

According to Sayeed (2011), agency costs and non-debt tax shield negatively affect the total debt ratios of selected Bangladeshi companies. Tax Rate, Firm Size, and collateral value of assets were found to have positive influence on Total Debt Ratio, while Bankruptcy Costs and Profitability were found to be insignificant in determining leverage ratios. Lima (2009) found that Operating Leverage, Growth Rate, Tangibility, and Debt Service Capacity are positively related to leverage in the pharmaceutical industry of Bangladesh whereas Agency Cost and Bankruptcy Risk are negatively related to leverage.

Hossain and Ali (2012) did not find any significant relationship between the capital structure decisions of companies listed on the Dhaka Stock Exchange and independent variables such as Profitability, Tangibility, Non-debt Tax Shield, Growth Opportunity, Liquidity, Earnings Volatility, Size, Dividend Payment, Managerial Ownership, and Industry Classification using OLS regression model.

However, the researchers found that Profitability, Tangibility, Liquidity, and Managerial Ownership have significant and negative impact on leverage by checking multicollinearity and estimating regression analysis through Pearson correlation and autoregressive model. They also found that Growth Opportunity and Non-debt Tax Shield have significant positive relationship with leverage. However, Earnings Volatility and Dividend Payment were not found to be significant determinants of capital structure decision among Bangladeshi listed companies.

Ullah et al. (2017) tried to identify the capital structure determinants of the textile industry of Bangladesh and found that the Age of the Firm has significant relationship with Debt Maturity. According to their research, Profitability has significant relationship with Total Debt Ratio, but a converse relationship with Short term debt and Long term debt ratio. However, the researchers did not find any significant relationship between growth opportunity and debt maturity.

3. METHODOLOGY

This research uses publicly available financial data from secondary sources for its calculation. Private companies had to be excluded from the sample due to the lack of publicly available financial information. At the time of this research, there were 18 companies listed in the Dhaka Stock Exchange under the food and allied sector. 14

of these companies were selected and their publicly available financial information over a 5 year period was analyzed using regression analysis to answer the research question.

	Trading Code	Company Name
1.	APEXFOODS	Apex Foods Limited
2.	BANGAS	Bangas Ltd.
3.	BATBC	British American Tobacco Bangladesh Company Limited
4.	BEACHHATCH	Beach Hatchery Ltd.
5.	EMERALDOIL	Emerald Oil Industries Ltd.
6.	FINEFOODS	Fine Foods Limited
7.	FUWANGFOOD	Fu Wang Food Ltd.
8.	GHAIL	Golden Harvest Agro Industries Ltd.
9.	MEGCONMILK	Meghna Condensed Milk Industries Ltd.
10.	MEGHNAPEP	Meghna Pet Industries Ltd.
11.	NTC	National Tea Company Ltd.
12.	OLYMPIC	Olympic Industries Ltd.
13.	RAHIMAFOOD	Rahima Food Corporation Ltd.
14.	RDFOOD	Rangpur Dairy & Food Products Ltd.

An Ordinary Least Squared (OLS) regression model was used with Leverage as the dependent variable and Firm Size, Profitability, Liquidity, Tangibility, Operational Ability, Sales Growth, Tax Shield, and Earnings Volatility as the independent variables. These variables were identified by our analysis of the previous research works mentioned in the literature review section.

Determinant	Calculation	Predicted Relationship	
		Pecking Order Theory	Trade-off Theory
Firm Size	Natural Logarithm of Total Assets	Negative	Positive
Profitability	Net Income / Total Assets	Negative	Positive
Liquidity	Current Assets / Current Liability	Negative	Positive
Tangibility	Fixed Assets / Total asset	Negative	Positive
Operational Ability	EBIT / Operating profit	Negative	Positive
Growth	Percentage Change in Revenue	Positive	Negative
Tax	Tax / EBIT	Positive	Positive
Earnings Volatility	Absolute Value of First Difference of Percentage Change in Operating income	Negative	Negative

The regression model is specified below.

$$\text{Leverage} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Size} + \beta_2 \text{Profitability} + \beta_3 \text{Liquidity} + \beta_4 \text{Tangibility} \\ + \beta_5 \text{OperationalAbility} + \beta_6 \text{Growth} + \beta_7 \text{Tax} + \beta_8 \text{EarningsVolatility} + \varepsilon$$

Aside from regression analysis, Pearson correlation was also used to measure the linear correlations of the selected variables. The findings of the OLS regression model were compared with the predictions of both the trade-off theory and the pecking order theory.

4. RESULTS ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The findings of the research are summarized in the following tables and discussed in the following sections. Table 1, Table 2, and Table 3 present the results of OLS method regression analysis. The model explains 73.8% variability in the dependent variable, with significant F-statistic ($F = 15.834$, $p = .000$).

Table 4 presents the findings from Pearson's Correlation analysis, where only Profitability and Liquidity were found to be significantly correlated with Leverage. Table 5 summarizes the findings of the regression model and compares it with the predictions from trade-off theory and pecking order theory.

Table 1: Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.027	.604		-.044	.965
	Size	.051	.029	.195	1.782	.082
	Profitability	-1.039	.586	-.238	-1.774	.083
	Liquidity	-.088	.011	-.809	-8.107	.000
	Tangibility	-.053	.017	-.266	-3.088	.003
	OperationalAbility	-.025	.053	-.037	-.472	.639
	Growth	.064	.116	.049	.551	.584
	Tax	-1.072	.332	-.446	-3.224	.002
	EarningsVolatility	.002	.012	.013	.162	.872

a. Dependent Variable: Leverage

Table 2: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.859 ^a	.738	.691	.1973491082094

a. Predictors: (Constant), EarningsVolatility, Tangibility, OperationalAbility, Growth, Size, Liquidity, Profitability, Tax

Table 3: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	4.934	8	.617	15.834	.000 ^b
	Residual	1.753	45	.039		
	Total	6.686	53			

a. Dependent Variable: Leverage

b. Predictors: (Constant), EarningsVolatility, Tangibility, OperationalAbility, Growth, Size, Liquidity, Profitability, Tax

Table 4: Correlations

		Leverage	Size	Profit.	Liquidity	Tangibility	O.A.	Growth	Tax	E.V.
Leverage	Correlation	1	.075	-.389**	-.690**	-.040	-.084	.036	-.146	-.136
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.535	.001	.000	.740	.489	.798	.243	.308
Size	Correlation	.075	1	.570**	-.415**	.045	.052	.246	.587**	-.171
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.535		.000	.000	.711	.669	.074	.000	.200
Profitability	Correlation	-.389**	.570**	1	-.071	-.019	.010	.455**	.722**	-.155
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.000		.558	.875	.937	.001	.000	.244
Liquidity	Correlation	-.690**	-.415**	-.071	1	-.105	-.035	-.266	-.337**	.287*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.558		.385	.774	.051	.006	.029
Tangibility	Correlation	-.040	.045	-.019	-.105	1	.004	.082	-.250*	.033
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.740	.711	.875	.385		.973	.555	.043	.808
Operational Ability	Correlation	-.084	.052	.010	-.035	.004	1	-.134	.026	-.044
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.489	.669	.937	.774	.973		.334	.835	.745
Growth	Correlation	.036	.246	.455**	-.266	.082	-.134	1	.336*	-.116
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.798	.074	.001	.051	.555	.334		.013	.404
Tax	Correlation	-.146	.587**	.722**	-.337**	-.250*	.026	.336*	1	-.234
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.243	.000	.000	.006	.043	.835	.013		.085
Earnings Volatility	Correlation	-.136	-.171	-.155	.287*	.033	-.044	-.116	-.234	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.308	.200	.244	.029	.808	.745	.404	.085	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).
 * . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 5: Summary of Findings

Determinant	Calculation	Predicted Relationship		Observed Relationship
		Pecking Order Theory	Trade-off Theory	
Firm Size	Natural Logarithm of Total Assets	Negative	Positive	Positive
Profitability	Net Income / Total Assets	Negative	Positive	Negative
Liquidity	Current Assets / Current Liability	Negative	Positive	Negative
Tangibility	Fixed Assets / Total asset	Negative	Positive	Negative
Operational Ability	EBIT / Operating profit	Negative	Positive	Negative
Growth	Percentage Change in Revenue	Positive	Negative	Positive
Tax	Tax / EBIT	Positive	Positive	Negative
Earnings Volatility	Absolute Value of First Difference of Percentage Change in Operating income	Negative	Negative	Positive

Firm Size is positively correlated with Leverage (Beta = .195) but is not statistically significant ($p = .082$). This is in line with the findings of Akbar and Bhutto (2012), however goes against the findings of Song (2005). Our findings suggest that larger firms in the food and allied industry of Bangladesh are more likely to use debt in their capital structure.

This supports the assumptions of the Trade-off Theory that larger firm size reduces bankruptcy risk and increases the likelihood of debt. However, our findings do not support the predictions of the Pecking Order Theory that larger firms are more likely to take debt as firm size reduces information asymmetry and allows firms to secure debt financing at lower cost.

Profitability is negatively correlated with Leverage (Beta = -.238) but is not statistically significant ($p = .083$). This supports the pecking order hypothesis that profitable firms prefer to use internal financing or retained earnings instead of debt. However, this goes against the assumptions of the Trade-off Theory that more profitable firms are likely to take more debt and benefit from debt tax shields.

Liquidity (Beta = .809, $p = .000$), Tangibility (Beta = -.266, $p = .003$), and Tax Shield (Beta = -.446, $p = .002$) are all negatively correlated with Leverage and are statistically significant. This indicates that firms with more current and tangible assets are likely to take more debt. Tax Shield was found to be negatively correlated with Leverage, which goes against both the Pecking Order Theory and the Trade-off Theory. This suggests that the firms that pay higher tax while operating in the food and allied sector of Bangladesh prefer to use retained earnings or equity financing when determining their capital structure.

Operational Ability (Beta = -.037, $p = .639$), Sales Growth (Beta = .049, $p = .584$), and Earnings Volatility (Beta = .013, $p = .872$) were found to be statistically insignificant in determining the capital structure decisions of companies operating in the food and allied sector of Bangladesh.

5. CONCLUSION

This research indicates that Liquidity, Tangibility, and Tax Shield are the three most significant variables in determining the capital structure in the food and allied sector of Bangladesh. Firm Size, Profitability, Sales Growth, Operational Ability, and Earnings Volatility were not found to be statistically significant variables influencing capital structure decisions.

Firm Size, Sales Growth, and Earnings Volatility were found to be positively related to debt. This implies that larger firms with high growth potential are more likely to use debt financing compared to smaller firms operating in a mature or declining market. Paradoxically, firms with volatile earnings were found to be more likely to use debt financing. This can result from either optimistic economic outlook or

desperation on the part of the financial managers. However, as these variables were not found to be statistically significant, this should not be considered conclusive evidence of their positive relationship with the leverage ratios of the firms operating in the food and allied sector of Bangladesh.

Profitability, Liquidity, Tangibility, Operational Ability, and Tax Shield were all found to be negatively related to debt. This would imply that highly profitable firms with exceptional operating ability are more likely to use internal financing (i.e. retained earnings) instead of debt financing. However, profitability and operational ability were not found to be statistically significant in the food and allied industry of Bangladesh.

Liquidity, Tangibility, and Tax Shield were found to be statistically significant in determining the capital structure in the food and allied sector of Bangladesh. As all three of these variables are negatively related to leverage, we can conclude that firms with higher amounts of liquid and tangible assets are less likely to use debt financing. Additionally, firms with higher tax rates were found to use less debt financing, which contradicts the Trade-off Theory of capital structure. Uncertain macroeconomic conditions in Bangladesh might explain the reluctance of financial managers to use debt financing and their preference for retained earnings.

Some of these findings support the Trade-off Theory, while others support the Pecking Order Theory. The causes of these inconsistencies were beyond the scope of this study and further research is recommended on this topic. Nevertheless, this study should serve as a valid starting point for future researchers and as a reference point for policymakers, financial managers, and investors involved in the food and allied industry of Bangladesh. Further research may also be done across industries to find out whether these determinants behave similarly in all types of business.

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